

The Role of Organizational Culture and Training Alignment in Enhancing Lecturer Performance

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine and analyze the factors that influence lecturer performance using an established research model. Key variables such as organizational culture, organizational structure, and training are identified as drivers that can enhance lecturer performance. This research employs a quantitative descriptive approach with a causal design. The population consists of lecturers from five private universities in Serang City, registered with the Higher Education Service Institute (LLDIKTI) Region IV and listed in the National Lecturer Database. A total sample of 176 respondents was determined using the Slovin formula, and the sampling technique applied was simple random sampling. Data analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS Version 26. The findings reveal that organizational culture, organizational structure, and training significantly affect lecturer performance. These results contribute to the development of knowledge management practices, particularly in managing human resources through cultural alignment, organizational support, and professional development. Furthermore, the study highlights the mediating role of job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior in enhancing performance outcomes. The findings can serve as a valuable reference for future research in the field of higher education management.

I. INTRODUCTION

A university's profile often encompasses various aspects of a lecturer's history, mission, vision, and educational and research goals. Each University or college has a unique background that shapes its identity and approach to higher education (Rosita et al., 2020). Many universities have a set of core values or philosophies that guide decisions and policies. These values may include a commitment to academic excellence, integrity, inclusivity, and Innovation (Salamun et al., 2021). Information on how the institution has grown and changed since its founding, including program expansion, infrastructure improvements, and student and staff growth (Winarno, 2019). This may include information on the University's significant achievements or contributions made in education, research, and its impact on society and industry (Terttiaavini et al., 2023). Recognition by national or international accreditation and ranking bodies is often an important part of an institution's profile, demonstrating the quality and standards the institution upholds (Maulana & Arli, 2022).

Institutions are seen as static collections of individuals in an environmental system, in which environmental subsystems

are interrelated and function directly to plan the goals to be achieved. (Aisyah et al., 2021). Competent personnel are essential for carrying out organizational tasks easily, efficiently, and effectively (Al-Masri et al., 2019). Humans are a source of power used to mobilize and synergize other individuals to achieve institutional goals (Isnainy et al., 2023). In business competition, an institution relies heavily on its human resources. Therefore, an institution ensures that its human resources possess the insight and expertise to perform their duties, which can automatically achieve its goals. Employees with insight and expertise are important assets that support the institution in maintaining the competitiveness of the industrial system (Setyaningsih & Sukono, 2022).

Law on Teachers and Lecturers number 14 of 2005, article 8 states that teachers and lecturers must have academic qualifications, competencies, teacher certificates, be physically and mentally healthy, and have the ability to realize national education goals. Next in Article 10, paragraph 1, teacher competencies, as referred to in Article 8, include pedagogical, personality, social, and professional competencies obtained through professional education. These four competencies are integrated into the performance of

lecturers. According to Article 1, paragraph 14 of Law No. 12 of 2012 concerning higher education, lecturers are professional educators and scientists with the main task of transforming, developing, and disseminating science and technology through education, research, and community service.

Lecturer performance results from a lecturer's behavior in the place where he teaches, or the implementation of ordinary skills that have been transformed into student learning. (Hidayah, 2023) . Lecturer performance is the result of an activity achieved by a person, based on the performance of each job, which is coordinated by an institution or organization, during a specific period. (Lumba & Waworuntu, 2020) . Lecturer performance can be seen as the result of completing specific methods or tasks. Therefore, all instructors are required to possess competence. Competence is the expertise and ability to carry out the responsibilities, tasks, or work entrusted to them. All applicable tasks and work include activities that process inputs and activities that transform inputs into outputs and add value to the products and outcomes of those activities. (Soares & Lopes, 2020). Lecturer performance is an important aspect in the higher education system, and it includes various factors influencing how lecturers carry out their teaching, research, and contribution to society and institutions (Sukirno, 2020).

Lecturers' performance is often closely related to their educational background, including their level of education (such as a master's or doctoral degree), specialization, and relevant additional training. Teaching skills, including the ability to structure and deliver course materials, use technology in teaching, and use effective assessment methods, are key factors in lecturer performance. Lecturer performance is also often measured through research and publication activities. This includes the quality and quantity of research conducted, publications in scientific journals, and contributions to conferences and symposia (Solihin et al., 2020). Lecturers' involvement in professional development activities, such as workshops, seminars, and conferences, can enhance their knowledge and skills, directly impacting their teaching and research performance. Beyond teaching and research, lecturers' contributions to the community and institution are also important. This can include community service, student mentoring, and participation in university administrative activities (Rahardja et al., 2020).

A good organizational culture is a factor that can influence lecturer performance. On the other hand, organizational culture is a framework that guides daily actions, makes decisions, and directs a lecturer's behavior to achieve organizational goals (Shea et al., 2023). Organizational culture is a pattern of values, norms, beliefs, attitudes, and assumptions that, although perhaps not explicit, shape how people act and do things. Values refer to what is believed to be important about how people and organizations behave (Glusker et al., 2022; Woodhead et al., 2022). Organizational culture is a system of shared meanings held by instructors that

distinguishes the organization from other organizations (Golrizgashti et al., 2022). Organizational culture is a pattern of basic assumptions discovered, created, and developed by a particular group, which is intended to help the organization face or overcome problems arising from external adaptation or internal integration (Gamage & Tajeddini, 2022; Petitta & Martínez-Córcoles, 2023).

Based on the background of the problem, the research objectives include testing and analyzing factors that can improve lecturer performance with existing models, with organizational culture and training variables, through job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior. Can accelerate improvements in lecturer performance. This research aims to Describes lecturer performance, organizational culture, and training at Private Universities in Serang City and Analyzing organizational culture's influence on lecturers' performance at private universities in Serang City. Analyzing the influence of training on lecturer performance at private universities in Serang City.

The contributions in this research include theoretical and practical ones, including the following Contributing to developing management science, particularly in managing human resources related to organizational culture and training through job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior in improving lecturer performance. The results of this study can also be used as a reference for future research. In Practical Terms and this will broaden and enhance knowledge of management science, focusing on Human Resource Management. This will provide a clearer picture of how existing theories align with the facts on the ground, particularly those related to the variables studied.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Resource-Based View (RBV) is a strategic management framework emphasizing the importance of a firm's internal resources and capabilities in achieving and sustaining competitive advantage. Developed in the 1980s and 1990s, this theory challenges the traditional focus on the external environment and industry structure as the primary determinants of a firm's competitive position (Battisti et al., 2022; Varadarajan, 2023). At the heart of the Resource-Based View is the idea that firms are inherently heterogeneous, possessing diverse resources and capabilities that can be leveraged to create value and differentiate themselves from competitors. Rather than focusing solely on the external industry landscape, this theory argues that a firm's internal resources—such as its assets, knowledge, skills, and processes—are the source of sustainable competitive advantage (Cruz & Haugan, 2019; Ozdemir, 2019). et al., 2023).

The Resource-Based View argues that for a firm's resources to provide a sustainable competitive advantage, they must possess four key attributes: valuable, rare, imperfectly imitable, and non-substitutable. Valuable

resources enable a firm to increase efficiency and effectiveness, exploiting opportunities or neutralizing market threats (Nayak et al., 2023). Resources are rare and not easily obtained by competitors, creating a unique strategic position. Imperfectly imitable resources are difficult for competitors to copy or imitate, often due to causal ambiguity, social complexity, or path dependency. Finally, non-substitutable resources have no strategic equivalent, meaning competitors cannot easily find alternative ways to achieve the same benefits (Ferreira & Ferreira, 2024). By identifying and exploiting these types of resources, firms can develop distinctive capabilities that are difficult for others to imitate, leading to superior performance and sustained competitive advantage (Gabler et al., 2023).

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Design Study

A research design is a framework that systematically plans and organizes research procedures. It encompasses the methodology and sampling techniques selected during the research. It encompasses the steps the researcher will take, from formulating hypotheses and their operational implications to final analysis, data analysis, and subsequent conclusions and recommendations (Ferdinand, 2014, p. 90).

3.2 Sample

The sample in this study was lecturers from five universities in Serang City, totaling 176 respondents, using the sampling approach method using the Slovin formula.

3.3 Research Location

This research was conducted at universities in Serang City. The primary subjects were lecturers at five universities in Serang City: Primagraha University (UPG), Serang Raya University (UNSERA), Banten Jaya University (UNBAJA), Bina Bangsa University (UNIBA), and Faletahan University (UNIFAL).

3.4 Data Analysis Techniques

Researchers use data analysis techniques to process and optimize data to find helpful information, test hypotheses, or make decisions based on the data. Descriptive statistics are used to provide an overview of the data being studied. Descriptive statistics are displayed as frequency values for each item answered in the questionnaire. An analysis was conducted using index analysis techniques to obtain a descriptive overview of the characteristics of respondents in this study, specifically regarding the research variables used. Inferential data analysis was measured in this study using the SPSS program tool, which was evaluated from the research model.

IV. RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Research Result

Descriptive statistical analysis briefly summarizes the data obtained or collected from a study. The population in this

study was lecturers at private universities that have become universities, namely five private universities in Serang City, namely Primagraha University, Serang Raya University, Banten Jaya University, Bina Bangsa University, and Faletahan University, with a total number of respondents of 1298. Those taken into the sample were 176 respondents with a purposive sampling technique, meaning only those with a minimum rank of lector and who have been certified as lecturers. The data includes descriptions of the research participants and descriptive statistics of the research variables. The research is categorized into five groups based on gender, highest level of education, marital status, age, and length of service.

Table 1. Characteristics of Research Respondents

Respondent Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage	Total
Gender	Man	101	100%
	Woman	75	
Last education	S2	158	100%
	S3	18	
Marital status	Marry	125	100%
	Not married	51	
	yet	29	
Respondent Age	20 – 30 Years	24	100%
	31 – 40 Years	59	
	41 – 50 Years	91	
	51 – 60 Years	2	
	> 60 Years	1	
Length of Work	15 years	75	100%
	6 – 10 Years	86	
	11 – 15 Years	15	
	16 – 20 Years	0	
	21 – 25 Years	0	
	> 26 Years	0	

Descriptive statistical analysis was conducted to provide an overview of the studied data. The descriptive analysis presented was in the form of frequency values for each questionnaire response item. A frequency index analysis technique was used to obtain a descriptive overview of the characteristics of the respondents in this study, particularly regarding the research variables used. Index analysis describes respondents' general perceptions of the

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questions/statements about the variables being studied (Ferdinand, 2014, p. 231).

The following are the results of a descriptive statistical analysis of the research variables: lecturer performance, organizational culture, training, job satisfaction, and organizational citizenship behavior collected from 176 respondents. To find the frequency index numbers in the descriptive analysis, the researcher used the computer-assisted software program SPSS version 26. Lecturer performance is the most important determinant of learning quality. Lecturer performance is the work results, both qualitative and quantitative, achieved by a lecturer in carrying out his duties by the responsibilities given to him, and is measured based on discipline, cooperation, obedience, attendance, professional competence, and workload (Hazzam & Wilkins, 2023). Four indicators measure lecturer performance variables through twelve statements, namely, indicators of suitability of implementation of learning tasks are measured using three statements, research and publications are measured using three statements, services to the academic community and the community are measured using three statements, and professional development and support are measured using three statements. Respondents' responses to indicators of the researcher's lecturer performance variables are presented in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Frequency Index Value of Lecturer Performance Distribution

Indicators & Statement Instruments	Frequency of Respondents' Answers Regarding Lecturer Performance										Index Value
	STS		TS		N		S		SS		
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
	1	2	3	4	5						
Complete the teaching of the material contained in the course RPS content.					11	6.3	86	48.9	79	44.9	4.39
Performing updates to the course materials with the development final			2	1.1	20	11.4	81	46.0	73	41.5	4.28
Adapting the Semester Learning Plan (RPS) to the current learning module			2	1.1	32	18.2	75	42.6	67	38.1	4.18
Average indicator of the suitability of the implementation of learning tasks											4.28
Do well in studies with fellow lecturers and involve students					8	4.5	88	50.0	80	45.5	4.41
Producing scientific works published in Sinta-accredited journals and reputable international journals			1	0.6	14	8.0	88	50.0	73	41.5	4.33
Attending national and international conferences with fellow lecturers and involving students	1	0.6	2	1.1	26	14.8	83	47.2	64	36.4	4.18
Average indicators of research and publication of scientific works											4.40
Carrying out the development of research results that the community can utilize			2	1.1	19	10.8	81	46.0	74	42.0	4.29
Carrying out thesis guidance tasks for students assigned by the Head of the Study Program	3	1.7	2	1.1	9	5.1	57	32.4	105	59.7	4.47
Enjoy providing outreach materials to the community			2	1.1	17	9.7	61	34.7	96	54.5	4.43
Average indicators of service to the Academic Community and Society											4.40
Try to achieve better results by taking training			3	1.7	19	10.8	77	43.8	77	43.8	4.30
Try your best to be better by taking training to develop your knowledge	3	1.7	2	1.1	10	5.7	51	29.0	110	62.5	4.50
Conducting research development from the training attended			3	1.7	15	8.5	60	34.1	98	55.7	4.44
Average Professional Development Supporting indicators											4.41
Average Lecturer Performance Index Value											4.35

The table shows respondents' opinions regarding lecturers completing teaching from the material contained in the course RPS content. The distribution of respondents' answers stated neutral 11 (6.3%), agree 86 (48.9%), and strongly agree 79 (44.9%). The average value of the distribution is 4.39. These results indicate that respondents strongly agree that lecturers complete teaching from the material contained in the course RPS content. Respondents' answers regarding lecturers updating course materials with the latest developments, the distribution of respondents' answers stated that 2 (1.1%) disagreed, 20 (11.4%), agreed 81 (46.0%), and strongly agreed 73 (41.5%). The average distribution value was 4.28. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that updating course materials with the latest developments is final.

Respondents' opinion statements regarding lecturers adjusting the Semester Learning Plan (RPS) to the current learning module. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that they disagreed (2) (1.1%), neutral (32) (18.2%), agreed (75), and strongly agreed (67) (38.1%). The average distribution value was 4.18. These results indicate that respondents agreed to adjust the Semester Learning Plan (RPS) to the current learning module. The average score for the appropriateness of implementing learning tasks was 4.28, indicating that respondents tended to agree strongly. The highest distribution of responses was among lecturers who completed teaching from the material contained in the course RPS content, with an average of 4.39. Opinions regarding lecturers conducting research both with fellow lecturers and involving students. The distribution of respondents' answers stated neutral (8) (4.5%), agree (88) (50%), and strongly agree (80) (45.5%). The average distribution value was 4.41. These results indicate that respondents strongly agree that lecturers conduct research with fellow lecturers and involve students. Respondents' opinion statements regarding lecturers producing scientific works published in Sinta-accredited and reputable international journals. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 1 (0.6%) disagreed, 14 (8.0%), agreed (88%), and strongly agreed (73) (41.5%). The average distribution value was 4.33. These results indicate that respondents strongly agree that lecturers produce scientific works published in Sinta-accredited and reputable international journals.

Statement of lecturers' opinions regarding lecturers attending national and international conferences with fellow lecturers or involving students. Respondents' answers stated strongly disagree 1 (0.6%), disagree 2 (1.1%), neutral 26 (14.8%), agree 83 (47.2%), and strongly agree 64 (36.4%). The average value of the distribution is 4.18. These results indicate that respondents agree that lecturers attend national and international conferences with fellow lecturers or involving students. The average score for the research and publication of scientific papers indicator was 4.40, meaning respondents tended to agree strongly. The highest distribution of answers was among lecturers who conducted a study well

with fellow lecturers and involving students, with an average of 4.41. Lecturers' opinion statements regarding lecturers implementing the development of research results that the community can utilize. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 2 (1.1%) disagreed, 19 (10.8%) agreed, 81 (46.0%), and strongly agreed 74 (42%). The average distribution value was 4.29. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that lecturers develop research results that the community can utilize.

Respondents' opinion statements regarding lecturers carrying out thesis guidance tasks for students assigned by the Head of the Study Program. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 3 (1.7%) strongly disagreed, 2 (1.1%) disagreed, 9 (5.1%) neutral, 57 (32.4%) agreed, and 105 (59.7%) strongly agreed. The average distribution value was 4.47. These results indicate that respondents strongly agree that lecturers carry out thesis guidance tasks for students assigned by the Head of the Study Program. Lecturers' opinion statements regarding their enjoyment of providing counseling materials to the community. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 2 (1.1%) disagreed, 17 (9.7%), agreed 61 (34.7%), and strongly agreed 96 (54.5%). The average distribution value was 4.43. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that lecturers enjoy providing counseling materials to the community.

The average score for the service indicator to the academic community and the public was 4.40, indicating that respondents tended to agree strongly. The highest response distribution was for lecturers supervising students' theses assigned by the Head of Study Program, with an average score of 4.47. Lecturers' opinion statements regarding lecturers trying to improve their performance by participating in training. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 3 (1.7%) disagreed, 19 (10.8%) agreed, 77 (43.8%) strongly agreed, and 77 (43.8%) strongly agreed. The average distribution value was 4.30. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that lecturers try to improve their performance by participating in training. Lecturers' opinion statements regarding lecturers trying their best to improve by participating in training for knowledge development. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that they strongly disagreed 3 (1.7%), disagreed 2 (1.1%), neutral 10 (5.7%), agreed 51 (29%), and strongly agreed 110 (62.5%). The average distribution value was 4.50. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that lecturers try their best to improve by participating in training for knowledge development.

Lecturers' opinion statements regarding lecturers conducting research development from the training they attended. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 3 (1.7%) disagreed, 15 (8.5%), agreed 60 (34.1%), and strongly agreed 98 (55.7%). The average distribution value was 4.44. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that lecturers conducted research development from the training they attended. The average professional

development/support indicator score was 4.41, indicating that respondents tended to agree strongly. The highest distribution of responses was among lecturers who strive to improve by participating in training to develop their knowledge, with an average score of 4.50.

Based on Table 2, the overall average score of lecturer performance variables is 4.35, which includes the suitability of the implementation of learning tasks, research and publication of scientific works, service to the academic community and society, and professional development/support. The highest contribution to lecturers trying their best to become better by participating in training for knowledge development, the distribution of respondents' answers stated strongly agree 110 (62.5%), agree 51 (29.0%), neutral 10 (5.7%), disagree 2 (1.1%), and strongly disagree 3 (1.7%). This means that lecturers strongly agree that they try their best to improve by participating in training for knowledge development. The lowest contribution to lecturers attending conferences both nationally and internationally with fellow lecturers or involving students was stated strongly disagree 1 (0.6%), disagree 2 (1.1%), neutral 26 (14.8%), agree 83 (47.2%), and strongly agree 64 (36.4%). This means that lecturers strongly agree that lecturers should attend national and international conferences with fellow lecturers or involve students.

Organizational culture is a set of fundamental beliefs discovered, developed, or formed by a particular group to teach the organization how to handle problems posed by internal integration and successful external adaptation. Therefore, it is important to teach new members how to understand, consider, and feel these difficulties (Ibrahim et al., 2017; Kaur et al., 2022; Mulyana, 2021). The organizational culture variable is measured using five indicators through fifteen statements: Innovation and risk-taking indicators are measured using three statements, attention to detail is measured using three statements, results orientation is measured using three statements, people orientation is measured using three statements, and team orientation is measured using three statements. Respondents' responses to the indicators of the researcher's organizational culture variables are presented in the table below:

Table 3. Frequency Index Value of Organizational Culture Distribution

Indicators & Statement Instruments	Frequency of Respondents' Answers Regarding Organizational Culture										Average
	STS		TS		N		S		SS		
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
	1	2	3	4	5						
Own flavor identification for innovation for the sake of increasing teaching, research, and community service			8	4.5	72	40.9	96	54.5			4.50
Providing ideas to advance the institution			16	9.1	69	39.2	91	51.7			4.43
Encourage colleagues innovate			3	1.7	61	34.7	112	63.6			4.62
Average indicators of innovation and risk-taking											4.51
Get used to communicating with colleagues			2	1.1	46	26.1	128	72.7			4.71
Follow necessarily in increasing development progress institutions			13	7.4	70	39.8	93	52.8			4.45
Provide suggestions to colleagues so that the quality of the Tri Dharma remains a priority			14	8.0	68	38.6	94	53.4			4.45
Average indicator of attention to detail and details											4.54
Conducting research every semester involves students			4	2.3	45	25.6	127	72.2			4.70
Research results with colleagues are published in accredited national or reputable international journals.			12	6.8	73	41.5	91	51.7			4.45
Conducting community service (PkM) every semester			15	8.5	66	37.5	95	54.0			4.46
Average of the Result Orientation indicators											4.54
Institutions encourage continuing education			20	11.4	65	36.9	91	51.7			4.40
The institution is planning to form a group to carry out community service (PkM)			18	10.2	83	47.2	75	42.6			4.32
Institutions give support for the Can productive			8	4.5	80	45.5	88	50.0			4.46
Average indicator of human orientation											4.39
Collaborate with colleagues to create learning modules			26	14.8	73	41.5	77	43.8			4.29
Collaborate with colleagues to design research			10	5.5	88	50.0	78	44.3			4.38
Collaborating with colleagues to design community service plans (PkM)			5	2.8	81	46.0	90	51.1			4.48
Average Team Orientation indicator											4.38
Average Value of Organizational Culture Index											4.47

The table shows the lecturers' statements of opinion regarding the lecturer's flavor identification. Innovate to increase the quality of Tri Dharma. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 8 (4.5%) were neutral, 72 (40.9%) agreed, and 96 (54.5%) strongly agreed. The average distribution value was 4.50. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that lecturers have flavor identification for innovation to increase quality, the three pillars. Respondents' opinions regarding lecturers' suggestions for improving the institution were as follows: 16 (9.1%) were neutral, 69 (39.2%) agreed, and 91 (51.7%) strongly agreed. The average score was 4.43. These results indicate that respondents strongly agree that lecturers suggest good ideas for improving the institution. Lecturer's opinion regarding lecturers supporting fellow lecturers in carrying out innovation. The distribution of respondents' answers stated

that 3 (1.7%) were neutral, 61 (34.7%) agreed, and 112 (63.6%) strongly agreed. The average distribution value was 4.62. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that lecturers support fellow lecturers. Carry out Innovation. The average innovation and risk-taking indicators score was 4.51, indicating that respondents agreed strongly. The highest distribution of responses to the statement was among lecturers who supported their fellow lecturers. Innovate with an average of 4.62. Lecturers' opinion statements regarding lecturers getting used to building good communication with fellow lecturers. The distribution of respondents' answers stated neutral 2 (1.1%), agree 46 (26.1%), and strongly agree 128 (72.7%). The average distribution value is 4.71. These results indicate that respondents strongly agree that lecturers get used to building good communication with fellow lecturers.

Lecturer's statement of opinion regarding lecturers participating in increasing the development progress of the institution. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 13 (7.4%) were neutral, 70 (39.8%) agreed, and 93 (52.8%) strongly agreed. The average distribution value was 4.45. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that lecturers should participate, thereby increasing the progress of institutions' development. Lecturer's statement of opinion regarding lecturers providing suggestions to fellow lecturers to maintain the quality of the Tri Dharma. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 14 (8.0%) were neutral, 68 (38.6%), and 94 (53.4%) strongly agreed. The average distribution value was 4.45. These results indicate that respondents strongly agree that lecturers provide suggestions to fellow lecturers to maintain the quality of the Tri Dharma.

The average attention to detail indicator score was 4.54, indicating that respondents tended to agree strongly. The highest distribution of responses to the statement was about lecturers getting used to building good communication with fellow lecturers, with an average score of 4.71.

Lecturers' opinions regarding lecturers conducting research each semester involving students. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 4 (2.3%) were neutral, 45 (25.6%), and 127 (72.2%) strongly agreed. The average distribution value was 4.70. These results indicate that respondents strongly agree that lecturers conduct research each semester involving students. Lecturers' opinions regarding publishing their research results with fellow lecturers in accredited national or reputable international journals. The distribution of respondents' answers stated neutral (12%, 6.8%), agree (73%, 41.5%), and strongly agree (91%, 51.7%). The average distribution value was 4.45. These results indicate that respondents strongly agree with the publication of research results by lecturers and fellow lecturers in accredited national or reputable international journals.

Lecturers' opinion statements regarding lecturers conducting community service (PKM) every semester. The

distribution of respondents' answers stated neutral (15%, 8.5%), agree (66%, 37.5%), and strongly agree (95%, 54.0%). The average distribution value was 4.46. These results indicate that respondents strongly agree that lecturers conduct community service (PkM) every semester.

The average score for the results-orientation indicator was 4.54, indicating that respondents tended to agree strongly. The highest distribution of responses to the statement that lecturers conduct research each semester involving students was 4.70.

Lecturers' opinions regarding the institution's encouragement to lecturers to continue their education. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 20 (11.4%) were neutral, 65 (36.9%) agreed, and 91 (51.7%) strongly agreed. The average distribution value was 4.40. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that the institution encourages lecturers to continue their education.

Lecturers' opinions regarding the institution's plan to form a lecturer group to conduct community service (PkM). The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 18 (10.2%) were neutral, 83 (47.2%) agreed, and 75 (42.6%) strongly agreed. The average distribution value was 4.32. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that the institution planned to form a lecturer group to conduct community service (PkM). The lecturer's opinion regarding the institution supports lecturers in being productive. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 8 (4.5%) were neutral, 80 (45.5%), and 88 (50%) strongly agreed. The average distribution value was 4.46. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that the institution supports lecturers in being productive.

The average score for the human orientation indicator was 4.39, meaning respondents tended to agree strongly. The highest distribution of answers was given to institutions that support lecturers to be productive, with an average of 4.46. Lecturers' opinion statements regarding lecturers collaborating with fellow lecturers to create learning modules. The distribution of respondents' answers stated neutral (26%, 14.8%), agree (73%, 41.5%), and strongly agree (77%, 43.8%). The average distribution value was 4.29. These results indicate that respondents strongly agree that lecturers collaborate with fellow lecturers to create learning modules. Lecturers' opinions regarding lecturers collaborating with fellow lecturers in designing research. The distribution of respondents' answers stated neutral (10%, 5.5%), agree (88%), and strongly agree (78%). The average distribution value was 4.38. These results indicate that respondents strongly agree that lecturers collaborate with fellow lecturers in designing research.

Lecturers' opinion statements regarding lecturers collaborating with fellow lecturers in designing community service (PkM) plans. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 5 (2.8%) were neutral, 81 (46%) agreed, and 90 (51.1%) strongly agreed. The average distribution value was 4.48. These results indicate that respondents strongly agree

that lecturers collaborate with fellow lecturers in designing community service (PkM) plans.

The average score for the team orientation indicator was 4.38, indicating that respondents tended to agree strongly. The highest distribution of responses was among lecturers collaborating with fellow lecturers to design community service (PkM) plans, with an average score of 4.48.

Based on Table 13, the overall average score of the organizational culture variable is 4.47, proven to be formed by Innovation and risk-taking, Attention to detail, results orientation, people orientation, and team orientation. The highest contribution is that lecturers get used to building good communication with fellow lecturers. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 128 (72.7%) strongly agree, 46 (26.1%), and 2 (1.1%) are neutral. This means that lecturers get used to building good communication with fellow lecturers. The lowest contribution is in lecturers collaborating with fellow lecturers to create learning modules, stating that 77 (43.8%) strongly agree, 73 (41.5%), and 26 (14.8%) are neutral. This means that lecturers collaborate with fellow lecturers to create learning modules. Training is a means of transferring skills, abilities, knowledge, and expertise to each lecturer, which is reflected in their skills and duties, as well as their awareness of activities in their field related to their work (Afroz, 2018; Z. Chen et al., 2023). The training variables were measured using five indicators through fifteen statements, namely the training material and method indicators were measured using three statements, the instructor was measured using three statements, the training participant criteria were measured using three statements, the effectiveness of the training program was measured using three indicators, and the training feedback was measured using three statements. Respondents' responses to the indicators of the researcher's training variables are presented in the table below:

Table 4. Training Distribution Frequency Index Value

Indicators & Statement Instruments	Frequency of Respondents' Answers Regarding Training										Index Value
	STB		TS		N		S		SS		
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
The training material explained by the instructor is easy to understand.					21	11.9	87	49.4	68	38.6	4.26
The training material explained by the instructor is related to his profession.					11	6.3	97	55.1	68	38.6	4.32
The training material explained by the instructor adds to knowledge.					9	5.1	70	39.8	97	55.1	4.50
Average indicators of training materials and methods											4.36
The instructor/presenter provides proper motivation for participants.					9	5.1	84	47.7	83	47.2	4.42
The instructor/presenter educates with humor					22	12.5	100	56.8	54	30.7	4.18
The instructor/presenter provides examples related to the tri dharma					4	2.3	96	54.5	76	43.2	4.41
Average instructor indicator											4.34
Given the opportunity to participate in training organized by the institution			1	0.6	15	8.5	91	51.7	69	39.2	4.30
Attending training with enthusiasm to gain new knowledge and skills					4	2.3	68	38.6	104	59.1	4.57
Completes the training completely according to the established schedule.					4	2.3	80	45.5	92	52.3	4.50
Average indicator of training participant criteria											4.46
Instructors/presenters can interact with Good to training participants					5	2.8	87	49.4	84	47.7	4.45
Implementation training, which is followed by the schedule that has been set					13	7.4	74	42.0	89	50.6	4.43
The training I attended provided knowledge to solve problems.					10	5.7	80	45.5	86	48.9	4.44
Average indicator of training program effectiveness											4.44
The training I attended provided positive benefits to my current profession.					8	4.5	75	42.6	93	52.8	4.48
The training I attended introduced new knowledge.					5	2.8	76	43.2	95	54.0	4.51
The training that I attended improved my abilities.					1	0.6	79	44.9	96	54.5	4.54
Average Training Feedback Indicator											4.51
Average Training Index Value											4.42

The table shows that the lecturers' opinions regarding the training material explained by the instructor were easy to understand. Respondents' responses were neutral (21%, 11.9%), agree (87%, 49.4%), and strongly agree (68%, 38.6%). The average score was 4.26. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that the training material explained by the instructor was easy to understand. Lecturers' opinions regarding the training material explained by the instructor are related to the teaching profession. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 11 (6.3%) were neutral, 97 (55.1%), and 68 (38.6%) strongly agreed. The average distribution value was 4.32. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that the training material explained by the instructor was related to the teaching profession. Lecturers' opinions regarding the training material explained by the instructor increased their knowledge. The respondents' responses were neutral (9%, 5.1%), agree (70%, 39.8%), and strongly agree (97%, 55.1%). The average score was 4.50. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that the training material explained by the instructor increased their knowledge.

The average score for the training materials and methods indicator was 4.36, indicating that respondents tended to agree strongly. The highest distribution of responses was that the training material explained by the instructor increased the lecturer's knowledge, with an average score of 4.50.

Lecturers' opinions regarding instructors/presenters providing beneficial motivation for lecturers. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 9 (5.1%) were neutral, 84 (47.7%), and 83 (47.2%) strongly agreed. The average distribution value was 4.42. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that instructors/presenters provide beneficial motivation for lecturers. Lecturers' opinion statements regarding instructors/presenters educating with humor. The distribution of respondents' answers stated neutral 22 (12.5%), agree 100 (56.8%), and strongly agree 54 (30.7%). The average distribution value is 4.18. These results indicate that respondents agree that instructors/presenters educate with humor. The lecturer's opinion regarding the instructor/presenter provides examples of the tridharma. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 4 (2.3%) were neutral, 96 (54.5%), and 76 (43.2%) strongly agreed. The average distribution value was 4.41. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that the instructor/presenter provides examples related to the tridharma. The average score for the instructor indicator was 4.34, indicating that respondents tended to agree strongly. The highest distribution of responses was for instructors/presenters to provide proper motivation for lecturers, with an average score of 4.42.

Lecturers' opinion statements regarding being allowed to participate in training organized by the institution. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 1 (0.6%) disagreed, 15 (8.5%) agreed, 91 (51.7%), and strongly agreed 69 (39.2%). The average distribution value was 4.30. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that lecturers were allowed to participate in training organized by the institution. Statement of lecturers' opinions regarding lecturers attending training with enthusiasm to gain new skills and knowledge. The distribution of respondents' answers stated neutral 4 (2.3%), agree 68 (38.6%), and strongly agree 104 (59.1%). The average distribution value is 4.57. These results indicate that respondents strongly agree that lecturers should participate in training, with the enthusiasm to gain new skills and knowledge. Lecturers' opinions regarding lecturers attending training in full according to the established schedule. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 4 (2.3%) were neutral, 80 (45.5%), and 92 (52.3%) strongly agreed. The average distribution value was 4.50. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that lecturers attended training in full according to the established schedule.

The average score for the training participant criteria indicator was 4.46, meaning respondents tended to agree strongly. The highest distribution of responses was among lecturers who participated in the training, with enthusiasm to gain new skills and knowledge, with an average of 4.57.

Lecturers' statements of opinion regarding instructors/presenters can interact with Good to train participants. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 5 (2.8%) were neutral, 87 (49.4%) agreed, and 84 (47.7%) strongly agreed. The average distribution value was 4.45. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed

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that instructors/presenters could interact with Good to train the participants. Lecturer's statement of opinion regarding implementation training. Which lecturer follows the schedule, as determined? The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 13 (7.4%) were neutral, 74 (42%), and 89 (50.6%) strongly agreed. The average distribution value was 4.43. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed with the training implementation and that the lecturer should follow the set schedule.

Lecturers' opinions regarding the training they attended provided knowledge for solving problems. The distribution of respondents' answers stated neutral (10%, 5.7%), agree (80%, 45.5%), and strongly agree (86%, 48.9%). The average distribution value was 4.44. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that the training they attended provided knowledge for solving problems. The average score for the training program effectiveness indicator was 4.44, meaning respondents tended to agree strongly. The highest distribution of answers was among instructors/presenters. Interact with Good to train participants with an average of 4.45. Lecturers' opinions regarding the training they attended provided positive benefits for their current profession. Respondents' responses were neutral (8%, 4.5%), agree (75%), and strongly agree (93%). The average score was 4.48. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that the training they attended provided positive benefits for their current profession. Lecturers' opinions regarding the training they attended introduced them to new knowledge. The respondents' responses were neutral (5%, 2.8%), agree (76%), and strongly agree (95%). The average score was 4.51. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that the training they attended introduced them to new knowledge.

Lecturers' opinions regarding the training they attended improved their abilities. The respondents' responses were neutral (1) (0.6%), agree (79) (44.9%), and strongly agree (96) (54.5%). The average score was 4.54. These results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that the training they attended improved their abilities. The average score for the training feedback indicator was 4.51, indicating that respondents tended to agree strongly. The highest distribution of responses was that the training the lecturers attended improved their skills, with an average score of 4.54. Based on the table, the overall average training variable score was 4.42, strongly agreeing, formed by training materials and methods, instructors, training participant criteria, training program effectiveness, and training feedback. The lecturer's statement that he attended the training was the highest contribution, with enthusiasm to gain new skills and knowledge. The distribution of respondents' answers stated that 104 (59.1%) strongly agree, 68 (38.6%) agree, and 4 (2.3%) are neutral. This means that lecturers enthusiastically participate in training to gain new skills and knowledge. The lowest contribution to the instructor/presenter educating with humor stated that 100 (56.8%) agreed, 54 (30.7%) strongly agreed,

and 22 (12.5%) were neutral. This means that the instructor/presenter educates with humor. Testing was conducted to answer the research questions or analyze the model's structural relationships. Hypothesis data analysis can be seen from the standardized regression weight value, which indicates the coefficient of influence between variables.

Table 5. Direct Effect Hypothesis Test

Relationship between variables	β	SE	p	Information
Organizational culture → Lecturer Performance	0.119	0.054	0.027	Accepted
Training → Lecturer Performance	0.205	0.055	0.000	Accepted

Organizational culture on lecturer performance, the study's results showed a coefficient value of 0.119 with a significance value of $p = 0.027 < sig = 0.05$, indicating that organizational culture has a significant positive effect on lecturer performance. The better the organizational culture in the institution, the more the lecturer's performance will improve. Thus, training on lecturer performance obtained a coefficient value of 0.205 with a significance value of $p = 0.000 < sig = 0.05$, indicating that training significantly positively affects lecturer performance. The more appropriate the training attended by the lecturer, the more improved the lecturer's performance.

4.2 Discussion

Organizational culture is shaped by Innovation and risk-taking, Attention to detail, Result orientation, People orientation, and Team orientation. Organizational culture in each indicator has a loading factor value of > 0.50 . The most dominant indicator value is in attention to detail and result orientation. Furthermore, training is shaped by training materials and methods, instructors, training participant criteria, training program effectiveness, and training feedback. Training in each indicator has a loading factor value of > 0.50 . The most dominant indicator value is in the instructor. Likewise, job satisfaction is shaped by a sense of pleasure, enthusiasm, wage expectations, appreciation, and suitability to the job. Job satisfaction in each indicator has a loading factor value of > 0.50 . The most dominant indicator value is in wage expectations. Likewise, organizational citizenship behavior is shaped by caring, politeness, a positive attitude, conscience, and wisdom.

Organizational citizenship behavior in each indicator has a loading factor value of > 0.50 . The most dominant indicator value is in a positive attitude. Lecturer performance reflects the appropriateness of implementing learning tasks, research and publication of scientific works, services to the Academic Community and Society, and Professional Development/Support. The lecturer's performance on each indicator has a loading factor value of > 0.50 . The most dominant indicator value is in services to the Academic Community and Society. Organizational culture has a significant influence on lecturer performance (Boichuk & Fast, 2017; Darimus & Hanif, 2023; Ezra & Charles, 2023;

Gochhayat et al., 2017; Hiswara et al., 2023; Rofiqoh et al., 2020). Research has shown that a positive and strong organizational culture can improve knowledge management, work performance, and lecturer performance in higher education (Hiswara et al., 2023; Muhidin et al., 2022). Organizational culture is reflected in the values, beliefs, and norms shared among organizational members, which in turn shape the attitudes and behaviors of lecturers (Boichuk & Fast, 2017; Darimus & Hanif, 2023; Ezra & Charles, 2023; Gochhayat et al., 2017; Rofifah et al., 2021). A strong organizational culture that promotes collaboration, trust, and learning can encourage faculty to create and share knowledge, ultimately improving their performance (Boichuk & Fast, 2017).

Training and development opportunities are also important factors that can improve lecturer performance. Empowering lecturers through support, information sharing, and role development can increase their confidence and innovative behavior (Thuss et al., 2016). Furthermore, effective communication and a climate that promotes professional relationships among members at various levels can contribute to a strong organizational culture and increased organizational effectiveness.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results and discussions in this study, the influence of organizational culture and training on lecturer performance is as follows:

Innovation and risk-taking reflect organizational culture in detail: Results, People, and team orientation. Training is reflected in the materials and training methods, instructors, training participant criteria, training program effectiveness, and training feedback. Lecturer performance is reflected in the suitability of implementation of learning tasks, research and publication of scientific works, Services to the Academic Community and Society, and Professional Development/Support.

Performance can be influenced by organizational culture. Developing an organizational culture that encourages lecturers to continue their education and publish research results with colleagues in accredited national or reputable international journals can improve lecturer performance by developing research results that the community can utilize. In the context of training, providing practical training, supporting the transfer of knowledge and skills, and offering organizational support to improve the quality of lecturers are crucial. Individuals who have participated in and received training opportunities tend to perform better.

In the context of training, such as training explained by the instructor, it increases knowledge and the instructor/presenter providing examples related to the tri dharma, this creates an increase in lecturer performance in producing scientific works published in Sinta-accredited journals and reputable international journals, carrying out the development of research results that the community can

utilize, this is due to the positive attitude of establishing good relationships with fellow lecturers, having responsibility for the results of work.

This research provides various important benefits, including: The research results can be a basis for university leaders to design more appropriate policies, especially in improving organizational culture and providing appropriate training for lecturers. This research also enriches the literature in educational management and human resources, particularly regarding the factors that influence the performance of lecturers in higher.

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